

PECULIAR ECOLOGICAL FEATURES OF POMEGRANATE VARIETIES
ADAPTED TO THE CLIMATE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotations: *This article provides general information about the varieties of pomegranates in Uzbekistan, their characteristics and the environmental conditions that affect them, and pomegranate grows well and produces abundant fruit in the eastern countries.*

Keywords: *ecological features, Mediterranean flora, Punica granatum, Dashnabad farm, mineralisation, irrigation.*

The pomegranate plant is present in the Mediterranean flora as early as the Tertiary period. The ecological characteristics of *Punicum granatum* L. are well developed as a result of long-term evolution. The subtropical Mediterranean flora, which originated in the hydrophilic tropics of the Mediterranean, has the ability to xerophytize with subsequent climate change (severe drought and cold), leaving a deep imprint on the ecological appearance of *Punicum granatum* L.

Pomegranate plants, which grow naturally in the northern regions of Central Asia and the Caucasus, are somewhat damaged by low temperatures during the winter. Due to insufficient frost resistance, pomegranate bushes are protected in many areas of Uzbekistan in winter.

G.T.Gutiev and A.S. According to Mosiyash (1977), pomegranate plant tolerates minus 12-16 ° in open areas in the territory of Azerbaijan, frost-resistant varieties tolerate minus 15-17. At minus 17-18 perennial branches freeze and hit the cold. According to BS Rozanov, VL Danilov, ST Skorokhod (1970), in Tajikistan, annual anomalous branches are damaged at minus 15-16 °, perennial branches at minus 17-18 °, and the surface of the bush is cold at minus 19-20 °.

In Uzbekistan, annual pomegranate branches, which are well prepared for the winter, are cold at minus 14-15 °, perennial branches at minus 16-17 °, and the aboveground part of the bushes at minus 18-19 °. In most parts of the country, freezing of the soil does not cause any damage to the root system of the anomaly.

Young plants are more susceptible to frost, especially early autumn frosts, than older shrubs, because the vegetation of young fruit-bearing plants ends late. Plants that open in the spring are more resistant to frost than those that are not buried in the winter. This phenomenon is explained by the difference in the environment of plant cells and tissues at different temperatures and humidity conditions.

Cold tolerance of pomegranate plants grown under the same conditions was also observed. In the 80-hectare pomegranate orchard of the Dashnabad farm, 14 years after planting, a single tree with a height of 3.3 m has grown, and the rest of the surface has been hit twice by the cold over the years.

For pomegranate is dangerous not only that the temperature falls below a certain limit, but also the nature of such a decrease and the characteristics of the cold period. In the cold period of the year, the weather in Uzbekistan is usually unstable: a sharp transition from positive to zero temperatures is common, especially in late autumn and early spring, when plants finish or enter the growing season. Sudden changes in temperature can seriously damage unburied pomegranate plantations. The less temperate regions of Uzbekistan are located in the foothills and low mountain areas, where temperature fluctuations are milder than in the lower valleys.

In Surkhandary region in 1968-1969 in Denau (at an altitude of 516 m above sea level) the temperature dropped to minus 15.6, the soil surface to minus 25.0 °. (900-1200 m above sea level) only one part of the annual branches and perennial branches were damaged. In mountainous and lowland areas, the low risk of frost is associated with temperature changes.

The degree of damage of pomegranates from the autumn cold depends on the condition of the bushes, their readiness for the winter dormancy. Fruit-bearing shrubs are more susceptible to frost damage than non-bearing shrubs because the crop weakens the shrubs and reduces their resistance to low temperatures. Those who are free from winter shelter and enter the growing season; Spring frosts of plants cause various damage to buds and twigs, leading to delayed flowering and reduced yields.

The cold tolerance of pomegranate varieties is not the same. Plants of the subspecies of red nodules, which include most cultivars, are 1.5-2.0 times less susceptible to frost damage than plants of red-necked species.

Pomegranate is a moisture-loving plant with a drought-tolerant appearance. Arealiturs of the genus *Punicum granatum* L. Are arid regions of Central Asia, but the pomegranate itself grows in the lowlands, along water sources where soil moisture is acceptable. It grows in drier and warmer climates, and in the mountains as it rises (to a certain extent). For example, in the Gissar Mountains there are anoraks at an altitude of 900-1500 m, and in the mountains of Baluchistan at an altitude of 2000 m above sea level (Symenoides, 1930; Osche, 1931; Vasker, 1951; Rozanov, 1961).

Prolonged drying of the soil adversely affects the size and quality of the fruit and leads to a sharp decline in yield. When there is too much moisture, pomegranate plants grow strong, produce less fruit and poorer quality fruit. Thus, the pomegranate plant belongs to the group of xeromesophytes.

Pomegranate plants thrive in areas that are evenly distributed throughout the rainy season and fall to 600-700 mm per year. In arid climates, artificial irrigation is required. The best quality fruits are obtained in the southern irrigated areas, ripen in the dry and hot seasons.

Pomegranate is a short-lived plant, like light-loving plants and other subtropical fruit plants. Shrubs that grow in shady places under trees grow poorly and bear little fruit. V.T

Chikhladze and A.I. According to Verin, the growth of young pomegranate seedlings slowed when the length of daylight was reduced to 10 hours.

According to GMLevin, SBKamenkovich (1976), pomegranate has a higher heat and salt resistance than fruit crops such as figs, mulberries and others, and a good yield at a mineralization of 3-6 g / l during irrigation. Will give. A.Sh. Gadjev (1952) observed good growth of pomegranate in sandy soils with a salt content of 0.87%.

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